

Quality Assurance Policy Implementation and Effective performance management in Higher Education Institutions in Developing Countries

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Abstract: Effective performance management in higher education institutions requires institutions to administratively adapt and implement quality assurance policy. Quality assurance is an education reform policy aimed to enhance the continuous improvement of higher education quality. The policy was adapted in African states from European countries as it originated from Italy: Bologna process accord of 1999. The Bologna process accord was preceded by the Sorbonne Declaration of May 1998 meant to increase students' and employees' mobility across different political boundaries in providing solutions to quality education and solving the problem of unemployment. Educational reform policies are best evaluated on the anticipated outcomes as a testimony of internal and external stakeholders' engagement in the system. The question of who are the stakeholders to effectively improve the performance of university and other tertiary education is the point of discussion. In this study, we accentuate the importance of human resource engagement in quality assurance policy implementation to enhance service delivery and product output in organisations like universities and other tertiary institutions. Empirical results show that effective performance management is achieved when staff participation is encouraged. It is empirically tested that employees contribute 68.5% success to policy implementation at the organisation level (Kibaliwandu, 2023). The anticipated mutual benefits that involve rewards, recognitions, promotions, increased revenue and change in standards of living for both employees and employers appear evident in national statistics of growth and development as a contribution from the national education system. Quality assurance in universities and other tertiary institutions is a key development indicator for UN-SDG Goal #4 as far as sustainable development goals (SDGs) that are discussed in the 2030 United Nations targets. Human resource management is an important factor of production in both developed and underdeveloped countries.

Keywords: Human resource management, employees engagement, rewards, recognitions, system management, effectiveness, efficiency and Performance.

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Introduction

Effective performance management in Higher Education Institutions is facing several hindrances starting from institutional governance, finance, political stability, security, scientific technology and innovation, and learners' attitude as well as environmental-related factors that would be addressed by the establishment of quality assurance directorate in universities (Kyaligonza & Kamagara, 2017). The concepts tend to be creating fear and panic among university staff hence resistance is noticed (Nkuny, 2011). Quality assurance is meeting resistance from both employees and employers because the working environment is not harmonized since the Uganda government has no standard for the wage bill in the country. This explains why effective performance management remains an issue of discussion in universities and other tertiary institutions in developing countries. Quality

assurance policy implementation is a reform policy within the education system aiming at enhancing the quality of higher education institutions. High quality includes high quality of knowledge, transferability of credits, labour mobility, transparency of academic grading system, research, employability and accountability to ensure the cost-effectiveness of the system (Cerna, 2013). Reform is the improvement of the existing system hence quality assurance is not new but a system aiming at improving institutional structures (normative theory). Normative decision theory is the study of guidelines for right action. It involves the formulation and defence of principles of comparative evaluation and choice among competing alternatives, proposed as rules that individuals or societies ought to – or perhaps would want to – follow. It deals also with the implications of these principles both on an abstract level and about particular types of decision situations (Fishburn, 2011). A normative theory states standards,

values, and proposals steps needed to establish standards and allows criticism for improvement. The normative theory presents arrangements and thus calls for change to create a better future for the community. The normative theory identifies what is right and what is wrong in a particular policy or system of organisational development and management. Quality assurance requires multi-stakeholders engagement in working to enhance the production of human resources capable of improving the gross domestic product (GDP) so that education institutions will be attractive and comparable at a global scale where mobility of students and employability will be observed. Then leaders can be able to mention human capital after investing in the creation of human resources. the Ugandan government is a signatory of the quality assurance system/policy as it subscribes to IUCEA (Kibaliwandu, 2023). The adaptation and implementation of quality assurance policy in universities and other tertiary institutions lack adequate information hence cognitive and behavioural ideological orientation is highly needed for effective performance management in the era of quality assurance policy implementation.

Quality assurance policy implementation suffers from a lack of knowledge, negotiation capacity between employees and employers, and empowerment of potential policy implementers who are the internal stakeholders such as the employees. The purpose of policy evaluation displays special competencies to establish the worthiness of the existence of governance and operation to build an efficient academic institution (Kibaliwandu, Mwesigye & Akena, 2018). The policy cycle has five stages; policy agenda identification or gender setting, policy formulation, decision-making, policy implementation and evaluation which eventually leads to policy termination or succession (Kibaliwandu, 2023; Fischer, Miller & Sidney, 2007). The confluence of several variables is at the point of policy orientation rather than economic environment as mentioned that SDGs may be achieved with little economic investment if individuals volunteer to share knowledge and implementation to achieve SDGs. Quality assurance policy implementation prepares suitable grounds for participatory engagement in science, technology and innovation that require staff collaboration in research and publication to document processes of innovation. This follows an epistemological premise that "teamwork effectiveness" has shaped the logic of the "input-process-output" heuristic formulated theory by McGrath 1964 which emphasize the engagement of individuals, team and organisation. The theory explores the influencing factors of the teams' interaction. The cognitive change is pertinent which is lacking in most public policy as several policies remain conference hall policies with little impact to the target population. The knowledge of good teamwork is closely related to engagement, productivity, creativity and satisfaction. Working in teams increases motivation and has numerous other social and personal benefits. People working in teams are more likely to persist with difficult tasks and enjoy themselves with done tasks.

Objectives

1. To identify policy cycles that influence quality assurance policy implementation in higher institutions' effective performance management.
2. To analyse the relationship between quality assurance policy implementation and effective performance management in higher educational institutions.

Methodology

The researchers used both qualitative and quantitative methods when collecting and analyzing data for this article. The researchers obtained ethical approval from UNSCT (reference SS-4248) where participants signed an informed consent form. It was agreed that raw data shall be processed and used in several scholarly articles on educational management and policy as needed in higher institutions of learning. A total of 182 participants from 6 universities; 4 private and 2 public universities actively participated in the evaluation of the quality assurance policy evaluation. The quantitative tool had a reliability of alpha $\alpha=0.762$ where CVI= 0.944. The researchers were able to observe both inclusion and exclusion criteria stated in the main document as a basis for enrollment of the researcher participants. The major variables for the study were cognitive awareness of the quality assurance policy, negotiation between parties, and empowerment in decision-making, anticipated service delivery that is evidence of the evaluation process.

Literature Review

The link between quality assurance and effective performance management is theoretically accepted to be the practice of participatory management. In organisation development, four systems of management exist; authority centred (top-down management system), benevolent autocracy (leader or politician utilizes absolute power over the state), the consultative system where subordinates are consulted to seek ideas and opinion, and participatory management with emphasis on consensus decision-making where both survey feedback and consensus decision-making are applied. In institutions of higher learning where quality assurance is applying multi-stakeholder quality assurance theory, consensus decision-making has been observed. The practical experience of quality assurance implementation entails teaching, research and community outreach. The quality of teaching and research is dependent on the quality and qualification of staff employed by the universities and other tertiary institutions. There is a "disguised clash of roles" among administrators/ managers and staff that originates from misconceptions and misunderstandings of the quality assurance policy. What is quality assurance? How does quality assurance work differently from education management? The policy is listed under transferred policies adapted from EHEA that has to be operationalized about its inception. Quality assurance provides a rich definition of terms and concepts such as effective performance management, benchmarking, collaboration, quality control, auditing, accreditation, assessment and other concepts aimed at improving the high quality of service and products. The concept of "effective performance management" is defined within the boundaries of planning, executing (act), tracking (giving feedback), and reviewing (identifying learnt lessons to plan corrections) for better results that appear not provided for by the office of quality assurance. Terms of reference for quality assurance directorate in line with effective performance management remain scanty hence unanswered questions cause doubt among employees. For instance, what is the relationship between the Office of the Academic Registrar and the Directorate of quality assurance? As some contenders assert that the creation of a directorate of quality assurance is a duplication of roles in the university, an evaluation of staff participation was rolled out by the doctoral candidate (Kibaliwandu, 2023). The whole process requires a department of monitoring and evaluation to be

established under the chief executive officer (CEO) or managing director of every organisation. The evaluation report should be supported by statistics that invoke administrative action and inform policy. The genesis of the quality assurance directorate in every university within Uganda has a background in data collection, data analysis and interpretation to inform policy.

Effective performance management should be guided by the five principles of performance management; performance leadership, performance planning, performance budgeting, human resource performance contracting and performance measurement. These principles work together and support each other as they are all based on planning, monitoring, developing strategies, rating and measurement, and rewarding or incentives. The process through which performance is measured and reported is an evaluation which was reported by several authors (Kibaliwandu & Mwesigye, 2021). The effective performance management system emphasises three broader elements; goal setting, performance review and a performance improvement process. All of these mentioned above define what quality assurance means to organisation development. Quality assurance emphasises the systematic process through which a team of participants is aligned to identify problems, analyse possible solutions, and identify possible resources needed for effective implementation of the process to avert the problem so that a product is brought to market with little or no defects. Participatory leadership leads to effective performance management with an emphasis on consensus decision-making. Performance management is about how much has been done while quality assurance is about how well the task has been performed or delivered. The process is documented to maintain and improve the quality of products and services. The process requires paying attention to both short and long term processes within institutions of higher learning. As mentioned that entrepreneurs can tell where every crack in the shop's floor is located and plans for repairs are always consistent with the damage. Performance management remains important to consider if it is essential for an "entrepreneurial mindset" to own all business details for institutional managers. The passion is marked by an intense and proactive curiosity about the problem of quality assurance implementation in institutions of higher learning. There is documented information on how to effectively improve management in organisations.

Peter Ferdinand Drucker's epigram of effective performance management identifies a few secrets of successful management that include; setting objectives, organizing the group, motivating and communicating, measuring the performance, and developing the people. The following also hinder effective performance management in African universities; low salaries of faculty, lack of research funding and laboratories or IT equipment, as well as limited autonomy have been some of the discouraging factors for qualified professors and students to stay in Africa. Brain drain is high because of poor working conditions and the academics and researchers on the continent work without the administrative support, grants, communication and public engagement assistance that their counterparts enjoy in a more rich research environment (Kasprowich, 2020; Ddungu, 2014). Environmental-personality correspondence is limited in most institutions hence labour turnover is high (Kyaligonza & Kamagara, 2017). The choice of African governments not to invest much in science, technology and innovation frustrate efforts of the scholars hence little is discovered

in most African universities. There is little engagement of government and university administrators that researchers work without grants, financial support and in a poor research environment (Kasprowich, 2020). This brings back the university and other tertiary institutions to the drawing board of the quality assurance policy formulation process. Effective performance management is guided by documented principles that provide coaching, training, support, time and resources to help the staff members to succeed in the production of products and services. The universities and other tertiary institutions have administrative tools ranging from those statutory instruments formulated or authored by the central government. There are policies formulated such as strategic policies, monitoring policies, and implementation policies have to be formulated by staff at the Institutional level. Handbooks like human resource manuals, Five years strategic plans, five years examination handbooks/policies, campus students handbooks, distance-evening and weekend learning programmes, research and publication policies, students admission and financial management to mention but a few remain guiding and authentic university administrative tools that are formulated based on consensus-decision making. These administrative tools exist on the mutual benefits between stakeholders both internal and external stakeholders. These tools are eminent for both private and public institutions since human resource management is a requirement for quality management. Performance management is of two types both personal and organisational and both are essential in the evaluation of employees' performance. The evaluation of any organisation or business follows criteria earlier stated during planning that measurements can be taken against the criteria. The core purpose of quality assurance is therefore to prevent mistakes and defects in the development and production of both manufactured products and services to the clients. Quality assurance processes empower business firms to review their internal and production processes consistently and create improvements in the production of goods and services. Methods of production are well documented and data is constantly collected for measurement and rates are taken for future improvement and maintenance of product quality.

Effective performance management is a function of quality assurance policy implementation in institutions of higher learning. The question of how well have we performed the task is quality assurance! Performance management and quality assurance involve common simple principles like; planning, doing work and making measurements, reviewing progress regularly to assess progress and evaluating effectiveness. Efficiency is defined in terms of things and its measure is quantitative while effectiveness is defined in terms of people and its measure is qualitative. Quantitative information involves inputs, activities, and output while qualitative information involves expected outcomes (what happens because of our activities) and impact that draws on contribution analysis to ascertain the predetermined theory of change which helps stakeholders assess and evaluate the worthiness of the project or institution. However, these may be influenced by the ownership, funding and model of social control and their impact on internal organisational characteristics such as managerial autonomy, goal clarity and economic incentives. The initiatives like Partnership for applied science, engineering and Technology (PASET) an initiative of the world bank that supports efforts of African governments in promoting science technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) initiated in March 2014 in Kigali where most African

governments were invited to invest in science (Diop, 2014). Universities in this case are the vanguards to Sharpe the innovation and development. University science enrollment remains low even after PASET. The gross enrollment ratio (GER) in universities and other tertiary institutions is sluggishly increasing due to priorities and community poverty levels in African countries. The overall GER for the African continent is 9.8% for tertiary education signifying that 91.2% of the population drop out of the education system before acquiring sufficient adequate skills of production.

The factors that lead to the successful implementation of policies include; an effective approach to the policy cycle, positive attitudes towards ending the existing problem, commitment to both tangible and invisible political “will” and collaborative behaviour between stakeholders. There is a poor network link between researchers on the African continent hence little information is shared between researchers. This is because researchers and academics work in isolation, little is tangible. However, as the African Academy of Science (AAS) funded by the Sub-Saharan Africa Network for TB/HIV Research Excellence (SANTHE) Consortium, research may be enhanced to improve high-quality education in universities (Kasprowich, 2020). Tracing concepts like (NEPAD) and others on the African continent so many initiatives but still science and technology are not gaining roots (Tijssen & Kraemer-Mbula, 2018). In 2002 Biosciences and Eastern and Central AfricaNetwork was supported by NEPAD in collaboration with the Canadian Government. Several policies are adopted under transfer policies that remain conference policies with little impact to change the lives of local community members at the grass-root level. Effective policy approach includes the five stages of the policy cycle; agenda-setting, policy formulation, decision-making, policy implementation, and policy monitoring & evaluation that may lead to policy succession or termination (Kibaliwandu, 2023). The cognitive or policy knowledge leads to the creation of a positive attitude of policy participants. Someone with a positive attitude in the workplace will bring an optimistic, can-do approach to all their tasks and responsibilities. Employees should be able to practice self-compassionate, not taking things for personal benefit but to work as a team. There is a secret to developing a positive mindset in working with others at a job or organisation. The team should be able to establish its commitment to both tangible and visible political and administrative “will” to ensure the deliverables of a particular policy. The administration should create an avenue for cooperation and collaborative behaviour between stakeholders at different levels of policy implementation. Public policies are possibly implemented under the four environments; the structural environment, the social environment, the economic environment and the political environment. These identified environments are created by the defined political environment guided by the cognitive value of the participants in leadership positions within the country.

Performance leadership is defined as a systematic, results-oriented approach to management and leadership for high-performance organisations, teams and individuals. Performance leadership creates a working environment for its employees to succeed in operation and production (Saidi, 2019). The management creates fundamental roles for their management and leadership teams to extremely high levels of effectiveness, basically working smarter to create conditions for success. The working environment may include formal cooperate aspects of the company like working

hours, workload, location of workplace from employees' residence, holidays and permits. The second factor for the work environment is associated with the motivational aspect where individuals, teams and institutions feel proud of their organisation. The third aspect of the working environment is internal communications employees should be informed on tasks and projects taking place within the organisation. There is the paradox of understanding the reality of African development trends; fertile soils exist and high poverty and hunger where Africa is proud of 60% of the global arable lands suitable for agriculture. Africa has 30% world's reserve of minerals yet it contributes less than 3% of the world's GDP (Gurib-Fakim & Spine, 2022). The reason is directly associated with a lack of performance planning and management. While Performance planning encompasses performance planning and management is a process to align employee goals to the organisational goals. The process allows for planning the alignment, providing management, support, monitoring progress and evaluating milestones. Smart goal setting, proper job description, focus on employees' professional growth and development, and provision of necessary tools including technology both software and hardware. Effective performance management has several other concepts that provide meaningful explanations for the application of the concept.

Performance budgeting: performance budget is a type of budget that reflects both the input of resources and output of services and products for each unit of an organisation. Performance budgeting aims to improve the performance of each budgeted task as per the budget. It is important to include performance indicators for the budget in terms of outcomes. For instance, the budget should be able to identify particular agencies involved and what each agency is to do and spend. The expected output and outcome create the availability of affordable services and goods to satisfy the final consumer in the production function. Employees' capacity and performance-based budgeting improve organisational performance as each task is evaluated based on cost-effectiveness. There are several ways through which performance budgeting can be promoted in an organisation. The purpose for which a particular university or organisation must be reflected in the mission, vision and slogan. The above explains why budgeting is important when considering effective performance management which requires an understanding of the goal and purpose for which a particular institution was established. The objectives should be tailored against each criterion and measurement for which the progress can be evaluated. The administration and management of both public and private universities present annual budgets to provide high-quality service to their clients who include both internal and external stakeholders. The internal stakeholders include both students and employees. The low morale among employees is associated with low incentives and the absence of rewards that are not provided in the annual budget.

Human resource performance contracting: In reality, science-related disciplines in universities contribute 29% of the African total research output. Africa contributes 2% of the world's research output which accounts for 1.3% of the research spending and produces 0.1% of all patents (Doip, 2014). Therefore performance contracting is a strategy used by the performance management system to achieve its underlying objectives. A performance contract is a concept that refers to a situation where a promisor and promisee have all to meet their obligations in the contract. The challenge between employment and implementation of the three

major core activities remains as research and publication have not been embraced by university employees in developing countries. For instance, only a 3% percentage of the articles published by university employees is by science-related researchers hence little has the African university scientists have contributed to science, technology and innovation. The scenario of administrative conflicts such Professor Mahmood Mamdani the executive director of Makerere Institute of Social Science Research (MISR) and Dr Stella Nyanzi in 2016 where the definition of contracts was misinterpreted leading to administrative conflict which was not necessary. There is staff resistance to change though support services that facilitate sustainable research are also inadequate (Kasprowich, 2020). A performance contract is a tool for improving employees' commitment to enhancing effectiveness and service delivery (Kemboi, 2016). Staff participation in quality assurance implementation is observed when teaching staff become active in the decision-making of how their classroom teaching experience can be felt outside classrooms through research and publication, project management of research in communities as well as community outreach service (Kibaliwandu & Mwesigye, 2018). In this respect, most private universities rely on part-time PhD holders from public universities who at times do not research and present papers on behalf of private universities. IUCEA defines full-time employees as those who serve 40 hours per week at an institution (IUCEA, 2010a). However, the roadmap does not distribute 40 hours into the three core activities; teaching hours, research hours, and community outreach hours (Kibaliwandu, 2023). This allocation of offices and compensation should be equitably made in employment performance contracts. Therefore performance contract is a legal agreement in which one organisation agrees to pay another when they successfully finish the project or task they were employed to do. The performance management contract is between the management and employees for specific tasks to be accomplished in the firm. It is important to contract employees for specific job descriptions such as

Performance measurement entails three aspects that ensure targets projected processes and expected outcomes. The performance measures require the presence of a strategic plan for the organisation. The strategic plan will highlight the following; prepare for performance measures, identify outcomes, create performance measures, and collect-analyze, and communicate results to the stakeholders. Teaching staff (lecturers) improvement and involvement is the only way to improve outcomes and students' acceptability of change in skill and knowledge revolution should be more scientific and innovative in providing new knowledge and development using research and creativity as a platform. There is a link between teachers' quality and students' outcomes (Verger, Altinyelken & Koning, 2013; Kibaliwandu, 2023). This can be detailed in the logic model that links inputs, activities, and output to the outcomes of the intervention or project.

An effective performance management system ensures that individuals and team goals are aligned with organisational goals so that performance done by individuals, teams and the entire organisation is of high quality to provide satisfaction. The advocated policy provides a culture of quality assurance that enhances human resource "effective performance management" organization to improve high quality of products to the market. These initiatives are closely associated with national economic

development in terms of goods and services that increase gross domestic product (GDP) and improve standards of living.

Quality assurance implementation and effective performance management

The link between quality assurance and effective performance management is the documented evidence of how institutions are ranked based on the five criteria; teaching, research, citation per paper, industrial income or research impact, international network or collaboration and reputation. The three new metrics used in ranking the best-performing universities are sustainability, employment outcome and international research network. A university that provides knowledge on how sustainable development can be done with little resources affordable to all citizens in a bid to combat climate change and sustainably utilize available resources through an emphasis on environmental, social and governance impact to improve quality of life on earth is significantly important. Quality assurance is an advocacy as well as a reform policy. However, as quality assurance policy implementation has faced several resistances, sustainable development goals (SDGs) in universities are meeting resistance. At the national level government leaders still fail to account for and evaluate the success of SDGs. Evaluation of SDGs in universities requires accountability, sustainability of projects and high quality of service and products that currently lack parameters in establishing standard rates of sustainability. Universities are known for teaching and research as core activities which also need to incorporate and measure environmental performance which promotes a culture of sustainability. The "input-process-output" heuristic formulated theory of McGrath of 1964 which emphasize engagement of individuals, team and organisation does not operate in isolation without structural leadership in institutions. The contribution of individuals, teams and entire organisation participation as inputs effectively supports the production process the outcome is a marked performance (Ishak, Nadzirah & Aziz, 2019).

Quality assurance policy implementation is desirable for effective performance management that has an output of increased learned citizens, transparency, accountability and sustainability. Institution growth has indicators such; as voice and accountability, political stability, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law and control of corruption. These identified indicators are the same indicators of institutional quality assurance. These indicators are reflected in national statistics such as GDP (Kandil, 2009). Institutional performance concerning higher education in any country takes on issues like budgeting, employees' salaries and wages, number of research and publications, international collaboration and projects, students' mobility and staff exchange programmes, patents and copyrights, new products and alumni established firms. These exciting ventures are reflected in the national statistics like budget and GDPs. Institutions whose salaries and wages take the highest percentage of the budget are bound to fail and it's a characteristic of poor performance (Davoodi, 1998). As several investment projects are initiated by the politicians, several managers of these investment projects will be willing to part with some incentives to political leaders hence little will be effective supervision. The end will show a high percentage of salary than returns on the investment which too will be wasteful ventures in an organisation. Therefore, quality assurance requires

accountability, sustainability and transparency for institutions to serve the citizens.

The university administration and management should be able to practice and make sure that the six governance measures; control of corruption (CC), government effectiveness (GE), political stability and absence of violence (PS), regulatory quality (RQ), the role of law (RL), and voice and accountability (VA) which are identifiable indicators for effective performance management in the organisation (Saeed, 2022). Performance in this case means doing something according to procedure with a defined outcome and output. Universities are manufacturing industries of knowledge and industries for products (Kibairwandi & Mwesigye, 2021). The six measurements used in government are hindrances to growth and development. The effect of corruption, ineffectiveness, instabilities, and lack of accountabilities deter development and growth. All these tend to reduce collegiality among employees because incentives and rewards tend to benefit a few of the employees in the system. Collegiality is another leadership strategy in the 21st century where employees' positive relation is exhibited in teamwork and quality improvement (Awbery, 2013). Academic tenure, collegiality, and academic freedom were being eroded in all universities especially in private universities due to low morale as a result of poor remuneration and compensation of employees (Rabah, 2015; Awbery, 2013). Ideally, all the six universities that participated demonstrate compliance and good QA practices that need simple enhancement to achieve the purpose fit for higher education in Uganda.

Human resource development through ideological orientation is an essential strategy for employees to conceptualize the production process. Employee engagement is the practice of supporting and recognizing your employees so that they feel more connected with the business. Performance management is as much about managing the context in which performance occurs as it is about managing performance itself (Saks & Gruman, 2011). Universities and other tertiary institutions support the learning process, research and innovation, review of knowledge and guide national development in science, technology and innovation. The universities are manufacturing industries for research and knowledge.

Data Presentation and Discussion

The data presents the status overview of quality assurance policy implementation as a basis for effective performance management in Ugandan universities as observed between 2017 and 2018 during data collection. Study participants represented the target population of employees in Ugandan universities. The quality assurance policy implemented by the employees either consciously or unconsciously based on what is observed is the product of the policy reality when subjected to evaluation. The report shows that the mission, vision, and purpose of establishing universities are part of the knowledge that employees should be able to understand. Policy formulation and implementation should be clear to employees because they are the key players in both policy formulation and implementation in institutions. Empirical data show that 68.5% success of the policy depends on the contribution of the employees.

Table 1. Testing knowledge of the employees in an organisation.

Item	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderately agree	disagree	Strongly Disagree 2.1%
I understand the Institutional mission, vision, and purpose and the knowledge makes me enjoy my participation	42.6%	31.2%	19.1%	5%	
Policy formulation procedure is clear to employees in this university*	11.3%	20.6%	36.2%	21.3%	10.6%
Employees participate in policy formulation at this university	9.9%	27.7%	30.5%	19.9%	12.1%

.adopted from primary data (Kibairwandi, 2018)

Institutions policies are formulated according to mission, vision and purpose. These policies are well known to 73.8% while 7.7% of participants have no idea of the organisation's mission, vision and purpose as shown in the above table. These live within the university organisation without any obligations to understand its effective performance management. It was accepted by 31.9% policy procedure was not clear hence a need to document the policy cycle for quality assurance practitioners in the university. As these processes were new and not clear 32% could not tell if they were participating in university policy formulation. Employees assume the consumer side of the products since they are not involved in policy formulation. In most cases, consumers take what is on the market in relationship with price. In the event of an alternative, they shift demand. This explains why labour turnover between 2008 and 2011 most university employees left; 68 employees left Makerere University, 10 senior lecturers left Gulu University, 15 left Kampala International University, 17 left Ndejje University, 19 left Kyambogo University, and 26 left Mbarara University (Ddungu, 2014). In 4 years, 155 university lecturers had left employment because there is no sustainable solution to improve the working conditions of employees in developing countries. The low salaries/wage as 87.2% of the university employees in Uganda earn less than US\$ 10,000 as their annual gross salaries. Despite the commensurate salary scale on public universities, few employees are on the government payroll hence a large number of employees are not on government payroll. The 87.2% of employees was determined from the sample and is supported by other researchers. For instance, Makerere University was lacking 49% of its employees to be employed by the government, Gulu lack 30%, Mbarara University lack 45%, Kyambogo lacks 44%, and Ndejje lacks 15%. These institutions are constrained by the financial challenges that are national. As the country can hardly fund its budget so do universities fail to fund their budgets. This explains why new funding sources should be thought of in an African way of doing this from scratch. The proposed Education Investment bank to provide a loan scheme has often been proposed (Kibairwandi, 2022).

When considering the chi-square between the level of sensitization and understanding institutional mission, vision and purpose, participants' Chi-square was $\chi^2=34.732^a$ with a likelihood ratio of 31.407 and linear-by-linear 0.791. This signifies that a relationship exists between sensitization levels and employees' understanding of the mission, vision and purpose of the organisation.

Table 2: The relationship between sensitization and employees' understanding of the mission, vision and purpose of establishing a particular university in place.

	Chi-Square Tests		
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.732 ^a	16	.004
Likelihood Ratio	31.407	16	.012
Linear-by-Linear Association	.791	1	.374
N of Valid Cases	141		

a. 14 cells (56.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.19.

The quality assurance policy formulation and implementation should be adapted and practised following the steps below as suggested by the participants in the completed doctoral research done from Ugandan universities. In this case, employees' participation in quality assurance implementation shows the high value of Pearson chi-square statistic; $\chi^2=34.732^a$ that signifies a high the more likely it is to be significant. The likelihood-ratio chi-square statistic $G^2 = 31.407$ is based on the ratio of the observed to the expected frequencies. The likelihood ratio that is greater than 1 signifies that the test results are associated with the usefulness of gender and type of school (Maate, 2023). The level of sensitization and knowledge of the policy cycle was positively correlated in this study.

The participants agree that little information is clear about the adaptation of quality assurance and implementation of normative procedures. For instance, 16.7% of participating Ugandan universities had not established quality assurance directorates in their administrative structures by 2017. It was agreed by participants like

Lack of Quality assurance awareness, Resistance against innovations, and Resistance of staff because they feel threatened by high-ranking employees within the system hence resentment towards the quality assurance directorate team. The possible cause may be little information/knowledge available in the universities on quality assurance as a policy worth implementing voluntarily" (IUCEA, 2010). It was further said by employees in the directorates of quality assurance coded as R095, R0146, R0159, R0178, R0145, R0152, R0138, and R0167 at different time and space suggested that these listed steps in table 4.07 were being applied when implementing quality assurance. The Participants coded privately above were workers within quality assurance directorates either as heads of departments or as office administrators. For instance, the participant (R0159) argued,

"We are four people in this office! We have been working as volunteers because we love the quality assurance system. We report directly to the Vice Chancellor's office and supplies we always get them from Vice Chancellor's allocation" (Kibaliwandu, 2023).

In the above, vivid experience above, Ugandan universities have performed up to 67.5% successfully in implementing quality assurance. The other percentage is accounted for by other variables not mentioned in the psychological tool that was used during data collection. Government policy, the nature of sponsors and students' demographic data were not included in the research tools. The opinion of students was captured in the observation tools as

semester evaluation reports were analysed as secondary data to ascertain the practice and engagement of the learners in quality assurance implementation in universities (Kibaliwandu, 2023).

Policy implementation success is held on the premises such as; vision building among actors, initiative taking or sharing tasks, empowering participants, staff development or resources provision, restructuring employees to undertake responsibilities, monitoring and problem solving, and planning for success (OECD, 2013). The policy cycle model provides five steps; agenda-setting step, policy formation step, decision-making step, policy implementation step, and monitoring and evaluation step that lead to succession or termination (Kibaliwandu, 2023). Policy implementation has got three pathways through which it can cause change in the community; top-down change where central government, region or local government will adapt the policy and emphasizes its implementation. The second pathway is "provider-based change" where philanthropic organisations will provide funding to evidence-based providers to work with the local community on a non-profit or voluntary basis. The third pathway is bottom-up change where high-capacity local government or non-governmental organisations not for profit will either proactively seek out and adopt existing evidence-based intervention concerning education. Adaptation pathways describe a sequence of policy actions or investments in institutions and infrastructure over time to achieve a set of pre-specified objectives under uncertain changing conditions. The adaptation of quality assurance policy in several institutions was introduced by the IUCEA (Inter-University Council of East Africa) in collaboration with the Germany Academic Exchange Programme (DAAD) and Germany Rectors' Conference (HRK) in the framework of their joint higher educational management support programme referred to as "Dialogue on innovative higher education strategy; DIES" (IUCE/NCHE, 2010).

The steps mentioned in Table 3 below were suggested by participants about an adapted policy or transfer public policy. The leader/ Manager/Principal/Administrator or Vice Chancellor has to take the initial step of orientation or making awareness of a new policy. In this case, it is quality assurance as transferred from European Higher Education Area (EHEA). The VC organize the appointment of self-motivated employees to take up the responsibility of the new policy/system of quality assurance. The first step is gender-setting, the second step shown in Figure 2 remains salient and step three (3) is step two in the policy cycle where employee engagement is done. After discussion, policy formulation is followed by implementation and policy evaluation. These make five clear policy steps into the complete termination and succession are recommendations for the evaluation step.

Table 3: The summary of steps taken in implementing quality assurance policy/system in Ugandan universities.

Personal engagement is the simultaneous employment and expression of a person's preferred self in task behaviour that promotes connection to work and to others, personal presence (physical, cognitive and emotional) and active full-role performance (Saks & Gruman, 2011). However, while the narrative from directors of quality assurance the directorate of quality assurance was not located on the official administration organograms of all participating universities by the year 2018 for Ugandan universities. Effective performance management in relationship to quality assurance policy implementation helps employees to actively participate in the policy formulation process.

Conclusion and recommendations

The policy takes five steps; a gender-setting, discussion, and policy formulation by the technique staff and it is presented back to staff, it is recommended to the university council for approval. The formulated policy may work as a working document not until it receives the approval of the council signed by the vice chancellor or chairperson of the university council. The approved policy is now officially implemented by the employee with the mandate of the university council. The University Council approves the appointed QAD employees are approved by the I. They are charged with the responsibility to implement and evaluate the policy implementation. The work of the quality assurance directorate is to evaluate and share finding for proper planning and implementation. in the monitoring and evaluation, internal and external evaluators may be allowed to provide reports. The evaluation aims at establishing a worthy lesson and proposal for the termination or succession of the policy. The researcher found that the quality assurance directorate faces challenges because they lack information on the policy cycle and how to implement particular policies formulated in universities. Quality assurance is both a system and a product that itself is a policy and when a system it allows other policies to be formulated and implemented within its framework.

Quality assurance is a reform policy in education that quality assurance is about how well the task has been performed or delivered. The policy cycle that influences quality assurance policy implementation in higher institutions for effective performance management should be followed. These policy cycles are; Agenda-setting, discussion, policy formulation, policy implementation, and policy evaluation that leads to policy termination or succession. In this article, quality assurance policy needs to have succession by enhancing process taking the example of table 2 above where; $\chi^2=34.732^a$. The university administration structure should be able to include a directorate of quality assurance under the office of the vice-chancellor. The directorate plays a role international evaluation process to enhance planning and management for quality improvement.

The analyse of the relationship between quality assurance policy implementation and effective performance management in higher educational institutions shows a positive correlation. The chi-square measurement; $\chi^2=34.732^a$ show also a strong relationship as evidenced by table two above. The likelihood ratio is 31.407^G signifying that the ratio is greater than 1 showing the test results are associated with the usefulness of employees' engagement in quality assurance policy implementation, and employees' policy knowledge through sensitization to enhance performance effectiveness in higher education institutions. The human resource

management policies should be created enhance working environment.

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Declaring a conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest as all data and information are for policy and institutional management to enhance higher education management.

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